

GRAPHIC NOVELS AS AN EDUCATIONAL TOOL FOR LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: Graphic novels are becoming popular among the twenty-first century readers. It is recognised as an important form of literature and has found place in the syllabus of several universities. It has become a valuable tool to improve the language skills of the students. Several graphic novels which are made into movies and series have captivated the younger generation. This paper tries to analyse the meaning, scope, characteristics, importance and challenges of graphic medium as an educational tool.

Key words: Graphic narratives, educational tool, graphic medium

Introduction

Meaning, Scope and Characteristics:

Graphic narrative refers to the long comic-strips which combine textual narrative as well as visual narrative. It enables the readers to visualise the context, characters, setting so that reading becomes easy. It is a process of reading and seeing. Graphic novels can be fiction, non-fiction, history, mythology, fantasy etc. It has a typical story structure, that is, it has a beginning, middle and an end and tells the story through illustration. Words in the forms of Speech balloons and thought bubbles are used along with pictures to narrate the story. Though Comic books use similar techniques in narrating a story they don't have a typical story structure as they contain only a part of the story. The first graphic novel "The Adventures of Obadiah Oldbuck" was published in 1842 by Rodolphe Topffer nevertheless, it was not known by the term graphic novel.

The term "graphic novel" was coined in 1978 by Will Eisner in his book *Contract with God*. Eisner describes graphic novels as a sequential art and a method of expression (Eisner, 1985).

Since then, the term is used to refer to book-length comics that have to be read as one story.

Graphic literature was not considered to be a serious form of literature for long. Over the years, due to the complex structure and plot, graphic novels have gained popularity among the matured readers. In graphic novels, the images tell most of the story. The text is used in a judicious manner so that the readers pay attention to the panels, frames, speech/thought balloons, colours, sketch of the characters, expressions, sound effects etc. These form the basic elements of any graphic novel. Just like any other literary text, graphic novels are stand-alone and do not require the support of any other formats. Like critical appreciation any literary text graphic novels also provides scope for analysis of character, plot, themes, conflict and resolution. Several serious social, political, cultural, moral, philosophical and psychological issues are also dealt by writers to bring awareness, criticize, condone such practices and discrimination. Many graphic novels, like classic literature, are also made into movies such as *Batman*, *Spiderman*, *Ironman*, *Wonder Woman*, *The Adventure of Tintin* and television series as *Smallville*, *The Walking Dead* and *The Human Target* which are widely popular across generations.

IMPORTANCE OF GRAPHIC NOVELS AS AN EDUCATIONAL TOOL FOR LANGUAGE LEARNERS - BENEFITS AND LIMITATIONS:

Realising the scope and benefits of graphic novels like any good literary text, academicians have shown great enthusiasm in incorporating graphic novels into the academic curriculum. Let us examine some of the benefits and limitations of graphic novels as an educational tool in language classrooms.

BENEFITS:

Communication skills: The primary purpose of using any material in a language classroom is to help students develop good communication skills. A curated content which can capture learners interest or evoke curiosity or that which promotes enquiry would kindle learners to engage in a conversation. Whether the conversation is intrapersonal or interpersonal it has its own utility in shaping their beliefs, values, attitudes and enhancing soft skills among the students. Graphic novels can engage a student most effectively in these prospects as it leaves readers with only images and text to associate meaning by filling the gaps. In this process a reader interacts within himself or with his peers or facilitators which unconsciously promotes language competencies.

Source: [Intrapersonal Communication](#)

Source: [Interpersonal Skills - Javatpoint](#)

Cognitive Skills: Graphic novels are considered to be an important tool to develop cognitive skills among the students as it requires them to read and relate the visual text and written text to infer meaning. Graphic materials help learners to respond and react, or to get emotionally connected and relate to their own experience or to question and evaluate the themes, situations, ideas or principles represented in the text.

Moreover, the use of graphic narratives along with textbooks makes even the reluctant readers develop interest in reading and also promote self-reading. It can help them overcome comprehension difficulties. Many teachers and students opine that the prescribed textbooks in schools and colleges lack colourful illustrations which makes it boring to read.

Analytical skills: Graphic text can occupy students in activities that initiate their higher-order thinking skills such as logical reasoning, evaluative comprehension, drawing inferences, express an opinion, illustrate opinions with examples, argue their case and sum up ideas.

Brodsky (2009) states that "The beauty of graphic novels in the high-school classroom is that they truly offer a multilevel reading experience for all readers. Students not only have to read the words for the plot but the images for the plot, too. By having students read on the two levels of text and image, they are not only improving their basic reading ability, but also their analytical skills—by evaluating how the images work with the text".

quoted in Biebrich, p. 27).

Creative, Abstract thinking and self development: Graphic novels can boost creative thinking, abstract thinking and promote self development. It can broaden students' horizons and understanding. Paying attention to the details of the images will help analyse people and situations from a new perspective as abstract thinking is centred around ideas, symbols, and the intangible. Analysing the colours can improve complex thinking and associative skills. Developing these skills amplifies an individual's ability to create creative material or to identify varied perspectives, contradictions, conflicts, problem solving or to associate meaning to signs and symbols of the visuals presented.

Literary Appreciation skills: Literary appreciation calls for understanding literary background of the author, socio-political and economic conditions of author's time, author's objective in use of setting, characters, theme, literary devices used etc. These literary skills will help the learner to analyse and judge the author's point of view in the context of his/her personal and general principles, beliefs and philosophies and their relevance in empathising or addressing past as well as current issues. Thus it promotes interpretative response of a reader, aiding him to not only draw delight but also to understand and appreciate the complexities of the text read.

Theatrical skills: Graphic novels can help a learner in comprehending non-verbal signals that are represented in the form of images in the text. The components of theatre skills such as body language, facial expression, eye contact, expression of emotions, posture, gesture, gait, coordination, stillness, timing, spatial awareness etc., are observed and internalised by the learners unconsciously. They will be able to emote the same when assigned with the task of role play or in a real life situation.

Language skills: Graphic novels can be used as an effective tool to develop language skills. Reading can be made more interesting and engaging through graphic novels. It enhances comprehension skills as the text in speech or thought bubbles are short and simple. It helps visual learners as images and colours are used to help. On the other hand they will be able to translate images into text or articulate their opinions and interpretations in written form. They will be able to summarise, write paragraphs or essays, dialogues or create parallel stories or use their creative and imaginative power to give different endings to the story. They will be able to enact and role play the sequence or story which illustrates their spoken skills. Since most of the graphic novels are conversative in style students will be able to pick up etiquettes followed when placed in varied situations and circumstances. They will also learn vocabulary required for everyday conversation with diverse people and context. They also help storytelling ability among students. They will also develop a fine understanding of grammatical structure and its nuances in a simple and lucid way. They will identify various tense forms, speech forms, voice forms, concord, antonyms, synonyms, prefixes, suffixes, homophones and homonyms very easily. They will be able to learn spellings of words as the text in speech or thought bubbles are less unlike a story in print form. They will also learn to understand word meaning in a context effortlessly.

Transmission of human values: Graphic novels like any spiritual text, novels, fables or stories can be used as an effective tool to disseminate ethics and human values through visual narration. Visual narrations have high reception and retention potentiality among learners of all ages. Values such as love, compassion, kindness, peace, charity, justice, tolerances, responsibilities towards the society, harmonious coexistence with nature, morality, freedom, universal brotherhood etc. can be transmitted intelligibly and conveniently.

Ethnopluralism: Wikipedia defines ethnopluralism as “Ethnopluralism or ethno-pluralism, also known as ethno-differentialism, is a political concept which relies on preserving and mutually respecting separate and bordered ethno-cultural regions. Among the key components are the “right to difference” and a strong support for cultural diversity at a worldwide rather than at a national level”. In this context, the availability of a plethora of multicultural graphic novels with varied themes, setting, culture, lifestyle and perspectives develops mutual respect, appreciation and acceptance of differences or uniqueness existing across the globe. It can also develop collaborative learning and inclusivity too.

Educational Tool: Graphic novels are not only effective tools for language or literature instructors but can be used by Science, Commerce and Humanities fields alike. If we analyse various graphical novels produced till now we understand its utility to instructors of other fields as well. There are various graphical novels available in various languages with their translations which widens the sources or materials at the instructor's disposal. For example Alicia en un Mundo Real (Alice in the Real World) (Franc & Martín, 2010), discusses breast cancer, whereas Epiléptico. La Ascensión del Gran Mal (Epilepsy. The Rise of the Grand Mal) (Beauchard, 2009), deals with epilepsy, Arrugas (Wrinkles) (Roca, 2007) is about Alzheimer's disease and Píldoras Azules (Blue Pills) (Peeters, 2004), talks about AIDS these novels can be used by medical and health instructors to educate on various diseases their cause and cure and they can also discuss about patient care and how to empathise with patient's family etc.,

There are biographies of scientists, historians, social reformers which can be used to create awareness about their life and achievements. Apart from this Indian graphic novel Delhi Calm by Viswajyothi Gosh can serve as the best tool for history instructors as it portrays the ‘emergency period’ in India. Hush by Prateek Thomas can be used by instructors of sociology and psychology to discuss child abuse and violence and Kari by Amruth Patil to discuss LGBTQ's problems and plight and on the other hand Los años del elefante (The years of the elephant) (Linthout, 2009) deals with suicide. The list can go on and on. We can conclude that graphic novels cater to teachers and students of varied fields and age groups by providing engaging and effective material for effective delivery of content in their respective fields.

LIMITATIONS:

Less exposed: A major challenge with graphic novels is that there is lack of knowledge among teachers, students and readers at large. Many of them are not aware of this form of literature and its benefits. Students are exposed to other genres of literature as they have access to them in various forms such as Print, audio and online. Whereas very few graphic novels are available online, the majority is in the print and hardly any in audio mode. Teachers on the other hand are also not exposed to this form as graphic novels are not considered to be serious literature. Those who are exposed lack training to use these materials. Teachers and policy makers are apprehensive to implement or to recognise graphic novels for their entertainment and educational qualities.

Limits reader's Imagination and language skills: One of the major limitations of Graphic novels is that it limits the reader's imagination as the setting, appearance of the characters, and their expressions are readily available. There is no scope for the readers to imagine these aspects and picturise them in their mind as they are reading. As the text used in graphic novels is very limited, it does not cater to the development of complex sentence constructions, writing paragraphs, formal language and thereby hampering the language and literary skills of the students.

Lack of depth: Since graphic novels emphasise more on pictures rather than text and try to narrate the stories with a limited text, it might not be able to bring layers of meaning in the narration. The stories cannot have a complex structure as it might confuse the readers when it is put in the form of visuals. Therefore, most of the time the stories will have a linear narration with a single plot so that the readers can easily understand it. Due to this, the stories might lack depth as the writers face the challenge of conveying things in a precise manner.

Misinterpretation: In case of graphic novels, the readers have to connect the pictures with the text. If the pictures are not clear or up to the mark, then it becomes difficult for the readers to bridge the gap between the pictures and text and make sense of it. If the readers are not aware of how to read the graphic novels; whether from top to bottom or left to right, it might lead to misinterpretation of the story. Even characters or colours sometimes can be confusing to the readers. In reality we cannot categorise characters as good or bad, they become good based on the number of times a character follows socially recognised values. Speaking of colours each colour can be used to represent or symbolise different attributes at different contexts. If a reader is not well informed on these aspects chances of misunderstanding or misinterpretation.

Curating materials is challenging: When we look at the history of graphic novels the content of graphic novels has changed over years. Even in children novels, there is some subtle adult content involved in it. Not only this but various slangs and abusive words or language that are used by characters can also have a negative impact. If The teachers, academicians and policy makers fail to recognise these content and ignorantly prescribe such novels in the curriculum, they are sure to taste failure in their objective. This threat in content curation has brought about a lot of resistance from the academicians as well as parents in incorporating graphic novels in the curriculum.

Need training to use materials: Lack of knowledge and training among instructors in the use of graphic novels in the classroom, has led to many teachers hesitating to use them in the regular classes. They also fail in recognising how these novels can be used not only in developing language skills but various other skills too. They are not fully informed to recognise various techniques, narrative modes and elements of graphic novels. Due to these shortcomings many are reluctant to use them as educational tools in the class.

Availability: Graphic novels are not available online for the readers to access it. Today the majority of them prefer to read on their mobiles or computers. Online materials are free or sometimes come with a reasonable cost. The cost of the graphic novels in print also deters many people from buying the hardcopies. The volume of some graphic series like manga makes it difficult to store the books. All these make the graphic novels less desirable for the readers.

Mindset of the stakeholders: Many people are still of the opinion that comics and graphic novels are for children. It is not worth reading for adults. They also feel that the storyline of these graphic novels are superficial and frivolous and do not try to understand the educational value of these novels. They also feel that reading skills, writing skills and vocabulary of an individual will deteriorate if graphic novels are prescribed. This mindset is also present among teachers due to lack of awareness and prevents inclusion of them in the curriculum. Parents also do not encourage their children to read graphic narratives as they feel that it has got no real content in it and might hamper the academic performance of the children. Students consider graphic novels only as a medium of entertainment and do not consider it as part of the main canons of literature and read it seriously to analyse, interpret and connect to the real life scenarios. All these have affected the importance given to graphic narratives in curriculum and the field of literature.

CONCLUSION:

A careful consideration of benefits and limitations will help us make a sensible decision about implementing graphic novels as an educational tool in language development. Graphic novels as examined can assist students to overcome various linguistic and language challenges. As it deviates from print only mode it can effectively engage the learners of diversified interest and distinct learning abilities. It also caters to the development of essential skills such as collaborative learning, critical thinking, problem solving, developing literary sensibilities, understanding serious concerns in the society they live in, Its scope for implementing various language learning pedagogies, imbibing values and ethics etc.

In this light a serious deliberation is needed in incorporating graphic novels in the curriculum. However ignoring evident limitations can cause serious impediments in fulfilling the aim and objectives of its implementation. Overcoming the limitations is not impossible. Creative writers should seriously consider creating sufficient valid material which can assist learners of all ages and fields. Teachers, students and parents should be educated about the novel form and its utility to the learners. Making the existing novels available to readers on public domains can also create interest among readers. A strategic and gradual implementation from elementary to university level by policy makers and academicians can actively reduce resistance and inhibitions that prevail among students, instructors and parents.

REFERENCES:

- [1] 10 Indian graphic novels you must not miss (2018) in *The Times of India*. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/life-style/books/photo-stories/10-indian-graphic-novels-you-must-not-miss/photostory/59016902.cms?picid=59016914>
- [2] Kowalchuk, I. (2017). *How Comic Books Can Transform Student Learning*. TEDxCU. [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iYA8Yxlar3E>
- [3] Mencini, A. (2013). Timeline of Graphic Novels and Comics. *Prezi*. <https://prezi.com/hllt-kvfanbn/timeline-of-graphic-novels-and-comics/>
- [4] Selene, N. (2022). *A Brief History of Graphic Novels*. [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8OYEBRdAINk>
- [5] Tato, D.B. (2016). A Brief Account of Graphic Narratives in India. *Sahapedia*. <https://www.sahapedia.org/brief-account-of-graphic-narratives-india>
- [6] The Bespectacled Librarian. (2022). *What is a Graphic Novel?* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Xe-FYIqrZrI>
- [7] Vidya Mitra. (2017). *The Graphic Novel and 'Literature' (ENG)* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=53T76OIWBrY>
- [8] Wright. (2021). *Graphic novel elements*. [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IZLh9XRxMUU>